

Health & gender implications of GHB-Related drug-facilitated sexual assault in Greece: A qualitative study

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ABSTRACT

Despite increased awareness, drug-facilitated sexual assaults (DFSA) remain severely underreported. Gamma-hydroxybutyrate (GHB), the substance most often implicated, poses distinct forensic challenges due to its rapid metabolism, yet these limitations alone cannot account for underreporting. This study, employing Constructivist Grounded Theory, explores GHB-related DFSA in Greece -a context marked by entrenched gender inequality, high sexual violence prevalence, and minimal GHB detection. Drawing on twenty-four interviews with key informants, findings highlight how forensic constraints, institutional inertia, and socio-cultural stigmas, particularly affecting women and LGBTQ + communities, perpetuate silence. The study advances an interdisciplinary framework, urging trauma-informed, inclusive reforms across forensic, legal, and social systems.

1. Introduction

Drug-facilitated sexual assault (DFSA) represents a pervasive and deeply concerning form of sexual violence that remains significantly underestimated, both in terms of its actual prevalence and the adequacy of societal and institutional responses (Skov et al., 2022). Characteristically, DFSA involves the non-consensual administration of intoxicating substances -most commonly alcohol and so-called “date rape drugs”- to incapacitate victims and facilitate sexual assault. Among the substances most frequently associated with DFSA is gamma-hydroxybutyrate (GHB), a potent central nervous system depressant with legitimate medical applications. Due to its rapid onset of action, affordability, and undetectability when mixed into beverages, GHB is frequently misused in social environments (Dufayet et al., 2023). Recent data indicate that its prevalence is gaining significant momentum across Europe: the 2024 ESPAD school survey estimated lifetime GHB use ranging from 0.3% to 3.4% among 15–16-year-old students in EU Member States, suggesting measurable early exposure across Europe (European Union Drugs Agency, 2025a, 2025b). Clinical surveillance data show a similar trend; in 2024, GHB/GBL¹ accounted for 10% of single-substance hospital presentations (European Union Drugs Agency, 2025a, 2025b). Law-enforcement indicators mirror these patterns: in 2023, 18 European countries reported 1269 seizures of GHB/GBL, totalling 51.5 kg and

nearly 740 L (European Union Drugs Agency, 2025a, 2025b). At the same time, the growth of the online market for GHB and its analogues has been accompanied by a reported 300% increase in use across specific recreational settings over a span of just three years (Palamar & Keyes, 2020). Alarming, members of the LGBTQ + community are nearly ten times more likely than their heterosexual counterparts to report using GHB in such contexts (Palamar, 2023).

Despite heightened public awareness in recent years, which has led to an increase in survivor testimonies, DFSA -particularly those involving GHB- remains substantially underreported (Busardò et al., 2018). This underreporting is attributed to a range of forensic limitations and socio-cultural barriers, including stigma, victim-blaming, and a lack of institutional trust (Tay et al., 2022). Women and LGBTQ + individuals, in particular, encounter compounded challenges in reporting, including systemic biases, inadequate investigative protocols, and enduring stereotypes, all of which hinder access to justice and increase the likelihood of re-victimization (Prego Meleiro et al., 2020). Women frequently internalize and normalize sexual harassment, viewing it as normal or expected behavior rather as violent acts. This inhibits disclosure and encourages silence in the face of abuse, as Hlavka (2014) illustrates.

Against this backdrop, the present study investigates the intersection of sexual violence, gender, and systemic barriers in the context of GHB-

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¹ GBL is a prodrug of GHB. Once ingested, GBL is rapidly converted into GHB by enzymes in the blood (particularly lactonase).

related DFSA, with a focus on women and LGBTQ + individuals. The research is guided by the following questions: *Why are GHB-related DFSAs significantly underreported? What institutional and socio-cultural barriers inhibit the reporting of such incidents?* To explore these questions, a qualitative study was conducted within the Greek context, namely a critical case characterized by stark gender inequality, high levels of sexual violence, and a conspicuous gap in the forensic detection of GHB despite growing anecdotal and empirical evidence of its prevalence (Poulios et al., 2022). The contribution of this research lies in its examination of the interplay between forensic limitations and socio-cultural obstacles in a largely under-researched national setting, offering new insights into the systemic underreporting of DFSA.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 conducts a literature review on the gendered dimensions of GHB-related DFSA, focusing on both forensic and socio-cultural challenges. Section 3 outlines the research design and methodology, situating the study in the Greek context and detailing data collection and analysis procedures. Section 4 presents the empirical findings, structured around institutional and forensic challenges on one hand, and socio-cultural barriers -including the experiences of LGBTQ + individuals-on the other. Finally, Section 5 offers concluding reflections, acknowledges limitations, and proposes directions for future research.

2. Mapping the under-exploration of gender in GHB detection

2.1. Forensic challenges in GHB detection

Forensic toxicology encounters significant challenges in detecting GHB-related crimes due to the substance's rapid metabolism and elimination. Because clinical effects occur within 30–60 min and elimination is swift, GHB is largely undetectable within 3 to 4 h post-ingestion,² making timely sample collection crucial for accurate detection and forensic investigation. Controlled dosing studies show that, with a standard forensic cut-off of around 5 µg/mL, GHB concentrations are detectable in blood up to about 3–6 h post-administration, with a large decline after 4 h and often below cut-off by 6 h (Faldborg et al., 2025). Consistent with this, forensic reviews emphasize that due to its short half-life (20–60 min), GHB offers a narrow detection window of roughly 6 h in blood and up to 12 h in urine (Steuer et al., 2021). Oral fluid (saliva) presents an equally restricted detection window: salivary concentrations peak rapidly and exceed forensic cut-offs (e.g., ≥5 µg/mL) within the first 2 h. By approximately 6 h post-ingestion, oral fluid concentrations generally fall below interpretive thresholds, rendering saliva analysis unreliable unless sampling is performed almost immediately after exposure (Faldborg et al., 2025). Against this background, numerous studies have emphasized the importance of timely sample collection (Chen, 2022), especially for DFSA cases (Busardò et al., 2018). A adding to rapid metabolism, the substance's endogenous presence further complicates toxicological assessments, *a fortiori* since gendered differences are present in endogenous GHB levels: males showing higher concentrations in hair in younger age groups, whereas females' levels remained consistent across ages (Vaiano et al., 2016) Controlled antemortem studies confirm that endogenous GHB appears at low but variable levels: approximately 0.0069–0.050 µg/mL in blood, 0.024–0.38 µg/mL in urine, and 0.034–0.93 µg/mL in oral fluid (Sørensen et al., 2024). Inter-individual variability in urine is particularly notable, influenced by both ethnicity and gender: men display lower concentrations than women in the hours following dose administration (Haller et al., 2006), and urinary GHB levels decline with age, a trend that can be corrected using the GHB/creatinine ratio (Crookes et al., 2004). Such physiological variations underscore the need for age- and gender-specific interpretation of toxicological results. In response to these complexities, Anderson et al. (2017) proposed rigorous sampling

protocols, including simultaneous blood and urine collection within 24 h of suspected DFSA.

Due to common collection delays, hair testing offers an alternative, though it requires precise methodologies to ensure reliability (Bertol et al., 2018) Toxicology evidence supports this caution, as in non-users, GHB in hair appears only at trace or very low levels (up to ~31.1 pg/segment), while alleged users show concentrations ranging from approximately 7.6–55.2 pg/segment, levels that still overlap substantially with endogenous backgrounds, making single-session ingestion difficult to confirm (Wiedfeld et al., 2025). While hair testing offers extended detection windows, nonetheless it requires careful segmentation and decontamination to distinguish endogenous from exogenous GHB (Berretta & Vari, 2020); segmental toxicological analysis of hair remains a viable method for detecting evidence of a single exposure to psychoactive drugs, even when conducted seven months post-assault (Carfora et al., 2022). A practical protocol for hair analysis has thus to involve segmental testing and ratio calculations to enhance accuracy in DFSA investigations (Berretta & Vari, 2020). The interpretation of hair analysis outcomes is impeded by numerous factors, including diverse substance incorporation mechanisms and the risk of external contamination. Inter-individual differences, arising from factors such as hair pigmentation, metabolic profiles, dietary habits, and the use of cosmetic products, add significant complexity to interpreting results (Larabi & Alvarez, 2023). Moreover, gender differences further influence these factors; for example, women more frequently use cosmetic products and may exhibit distinct hair color patterns, potentially affecting sample characteristics. In addition, variations in sweat composition between genders are critical, as sweat contamination can compromise the reliability of the sample. Consequently, researchers advocate for a two-phase hair sampling approach for GHB detection (de Souza Costa et al., 2020): an initial sample should be collected as soon as possible after exposure, and a second sample should be obtained one month later. Both samples must undergo identical treatment and analysis, with a comparative evaluation of GHB concentrations in corresponding hair segments. Notably, the first segment should be excluded from analysis due to its increased risk of sweat contamination.

Due to these difficulties in toxicological assessments new detection strategies shift the focus from the DFSA victims to the means of their intoxication. On-site detection in beverages can aid crime prevention and enhance investigate efficiency by utilizing portable detection methods, such as the GHB-specific colorimetric sensors (Son et al., 2021) that can provide immediate screening options at suspected crime scenes. Still these techniques don't come without challenges, since natural GHB presence for instance in energy drinks might be misinterpreted (Vaiano & Umami Ronchi, 2020). There is thus a need for stringent criteria and integrated toxicological screening methods to distinguish exogenous GHB in forensic analyses, not least since there is often a combination of alcohol and proactive drugs alongside GHB in DFSA cases (Bertol et al., 2018). Individuals consuming GHB alongside alcohol face exponentially higher risks of incapacitation and subsequent victimization (Lynam et al., 2024). GHB co-ingested with ethanol, has been proven to expand its sedative effects and increase susceptibility to crimes (Kapitány Fövényi et al., 2017). Along these lines, the inclusion of multi-drug testing can ensure a more comprehensive detection of the interplay of substances often present in such DFSA.

Even within the complexities of forensic evidence collection, a significant gap remains in accurately correlating physiological metrics with real-time crime reporting (Chen, 2022), posing numerous challenges. One major issue is delayed reporting, which is particularly prevalent among female victims of DFSA due to fear, shame, and a lack of procedural knowledge (de Souza Costa et al., 2020). Additionally, the absence of trauma-informed policing plays a crucial role in discouraging survivors from disclosing their experiences, further complicating investigations (Stewart et al., 2023). Despite these barriers, research indicates that women are more likely than men to report assaults to emergency services and undergo forensic examinations (Fernández

² <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK430781/>.

Alonso et al., 2024). In contrast, male survivors face even greater stigmatization, which often results in severe underreporting. The lack of reporting by men has led to existing forensic protocols being predominantly tailored to female victims, inadvertently overlooking male and LGBTQ + survivors. Addressing this systemic exclusion is crucial for ensuring equitable justice for all victims, regardless of gender or sexual orientation. Moreover, discriminatory practices within the criminal justice system further marginalize LGBTQ + victims, who frequently encounter institutional biases and barriers to accessing justice (McMillan, 2016). Expanding forensic and legal protocols to account for the diverse experiences of all survivors is imperative in creating a more inclusive and just system.

2.2. Socio-cultural challenges in reporting DFSAs

Empirically, GHB continues to attract significant social attention, as reports of “rape drug” incidents are becoming increasingly frequent. However, a recent comprehensive review of toxicological findings in DFSA Cases –10680 cases from 16 countries from 1996 to 2018- indicated low overall rates of GHB in DFSA crimes with most victims being women aged 23.7 to 31.4 years (Skov et al., 2022). Identified in a range between 0.2% and 5.9% the higher percentages were observed in the United States (5.9%), France (3.0%) and the Netherlands (2.0%), while the lowest percentages were observed in Canada (1.1%), the United Kingdom (0.2%), and Italy (0.4%) (Skov et al., 2022). The findings appear to support the conventional view that GHB-facilitated DFSA cases predominantly affect young women. However, the reported rates remain lower than what social experience and anecdotal evidence suggest, highlighting a potential underreporting issue or gaps in forensic detection. This discrepancy warrants further investigation to uncover the true prevalence and contributing factors behind these cases. Hlavka (2014) uses interviews with teenage females to demonstrate how sexual harassment and abuse are frequently ingrained in daily life, so ubiquitous that many young women do not even recognize them as violent. Due to internalized normality and social disbelief, girls frequently use heteronormative norms like “boys will be boys” to justify such behaviors rather than seeing them as exceptional.

Delving into these phenomena, the findings suggest that these patterns stem not only from the challenges of effectively detecting GHB (Busardò et al., 2018) but also from the difficulty in distinguishing its recreational use from its highly exploitable disinhibitory effects, which frequently play a role in DFSA crimes (Tay et al., 2022). This recreational context often overlaps with chemsex, which is broadly defined as a specific subset of sexualized drug use, operationalized through the intentional use of crystal methamphetamine, mephedrone, and GHB/GBL before or during sex. Chemsex serves not only to intensify, extend, and amplify sexual experiences, but also as a context in which individuals experiment with gender and sexual identities (Poulios, 2022). This points to a largely unexplored yet particularly vicious phenomenon, especially within the LGBTQ + community: clinical surveillance data from single-substance hospital presentations indicate that GHB/GBL accounts for 10% of cases, with a median patient age of 35 years and a predominance of male patients (80%) (European Union Drugs Agency, 2025a, 2025b). In this regard, the normalization of chemsex-related activities complicates the societal framing of consensual versus coerced substance use, with implications for both legal and medical interventions (Palamar, 2022).

Although some individuals manage their chemsex practices without developing significant complications, the physical and mental health consequences associated with chemsex, including infections, dependence, and psychological distress, are becoming increasingly common (Le Bouédec et al., 2025). A randomized controlled trial found that a harm-reduction-oriented web-based programme significantly increased Men having sex with Men (MSM) participants’ self-efficacy to refuse risky sexual behaviours and chemsex, reduced both the intention and likelihood of engaging in chemsex, and improved HIV testing uptake

(Choi et al., 2023). This aligns with broader recommendations that chemsex interventions should emphasize safer-use knowledge, dosing strategies, condom-use self-efficacy, and STI/HIV prevention, recognizing that abstinence-based models are not realistic for many users (European Union Drugs Agency, 2025a, 2025b).

Taken together, this emerging evidence supports the argument that chemsex should be conceptualized as a complex syndemic phenomenon that requires standardized definitions, targeted harm-reduction interventions, and systematic examination of drug-sexual behaviour interactions (Coronado-Muñoz et al., 2024). GHB-involved chemsex environments can therefore produce situations of chemical submission, where intoxication impairs an individual’s capacity to act autonomously and disrupts their ability to communicate or withdraw consent. This dynamic gives rise to what has been described as “blurred consent,” in which substance-induced impairment obscures the distinction between voluntary participation and coercion, as diminished awareness, judgment, memory, and resistance render consent unstable or ambiguous (Lee et al., 2024).

An analysis of 408 GHB-intoxication cases indicated that 6.5% of unintentional cases involved sexual assault, while 21.7% were even linked to acquisitory crimes, predominantly affecting males (Kapitány Fövényi et al., 2017). In this context, heavy GHB users who experienced GHB-induced comas exhibited lower self-control and higher negative affect. These individuals predominantly consumed GHB alone at home, contrasting with social use among non-coma participants. Such distinctions in usage patterns have further implications for both prevention and treatment strategies (Raposo Pereira et al., 2020). Along these lines, research indicates that gay men were significantly more likely to use GHB compared to heterosexual men (Palamar, 2022) while most GHB-related deaths involved young males using the substance recreationally, often in combination with other drugs (Darke et al., 2020).

In this context of chemsex, the intersection of substance use and gender dynamics is particularly important, since male DFSA victims often face victim blaming, with social narratives framing them as complicit. For male victims, societal constructions of masculinity exacerbate underreporting. Javaid (2014) argued that male sexual assault victims challenge hegemonic masculinity, leading to stigmatization and neglect. Expanding on these observations, Frizzell et al. (2021) contend that gendered sexual identities influence how people perceive and cope with stress, especially when they participate in risky activities like using drugs during sexual activity. Furthermore, because portable GHB detection kits often resemble eyeshadow boxes (Zhang, Zhao, Zhang, & colleagues, 2024), male victims may be reluctant to use them for fear of reinforcing gender-based stigmatization. These cultural attitudes perpetuate victimization in DFSA, leading to a lack of social support and inadequate coping mechanisms that contribute to cycles of substance abuse and re-victimization (Prego Meleiro et al., 2020). All these sociocultural biases reinforce societal stigmas, deterring victims from seeking help and perpetuating cycles of violence. This dynamic is evident even in high-profile cases, such as those involving Stephen Port and Reinhard Sinaga, where media narratives and police biases influenced the handling of male victimization (Lee et al., 2024). These cases underscore the intersection of societal biases, media representation, and judicial oversight, which often results in diminished advocacy for male survivors of GHB-related crimes.

Expanding forensic capabilities, such as on-site detection tools through “violet points”,³ and advanced analytical methods, can help overcome the challenges posed by GHB’s rapid metabolism (Son et al., 2021). Such a quest must be embedded within a broader public awareness effort aimed at reducing stigma, encouraging timely reporting, and strengthening trauma-informed training for law enforcement and healthcare professionals to improve victim support and

³ <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/world/europe/violet-point-medus-a-sunbeach-festival-b2595468.html>.

investigative outcomes (Stewart et al., 2023). In parallel with these awareness-raising initiatives, interdisciplinary field research is essential for understanding the sociocultural dynamics of GHB use and its contribution to patterns of victimization. Moreover, further studies on the physiological effects of GHB across diverse demographic groups (Vaiano et al., 2016) are needed to inform the development of tailored forensic and medical interventions.

3. Research design and methodology

3.1. Contextualizing the research: why Greece as a case study?

The coexistence of multiple, ambivalent gender ideologies is most striking in Southern and Central/Eastern Europe, indicating a transitional, unstable equilibrium in the region's gender-normative landscape (Begall et al., 2023). Institutional research across Mediterranean professional settings documents pervasive silencing and disbelief toward victims, mechanisms that reproduce gendered power asymmetries and sustain environments permissive of harassment and abuse (Searle & Garippa, 2025), reflecting deeper intersectional gaps in institutional responses to gendered violence (Bowleg et al., 2023). This is closely related to the fact that state-recognized categories of gender violence often end up excluding intersectional realities (Pamplona, 2025). A 2024 cross-cultural study from Spain found that 17% of women and 15% of men aged 18–27 had experienced sexual violence in party/nightlife contexts, environments where DFSA commonly occurs (Prego-Meleiro et al., 2024). Similarly, a 2025 study from Poland reported that approximately 10% of young adults had experienced drug-facilitated sexual assault in party-related settings, with women, young adults, and sexual minorities disproportionately affected (Silczuk et al., 2025). Clinical evidence from Southern Europe aligns with these findings: a retrospective study in Barcelona indicated that substances are involved in about one-third of sexual assault cases, with GHB more commonly reported among male victims (Camps et al., 2024).

Greece presents a compelling case study for examining the gender aspects of forensic and legal challenges associated with GHB-related DFSA due to its combination of legal gaps, forensic limitations, and socio-cultural barriers. Traditionalist norms remain particularly resistant to change, reflected in widespread support for conventional domestic gender roles. Greece therefore aligns with a broader Mediterranean pattern in which gender norms remain highly prescriptive, constraining women's autonomy through expectations of femininity, respectability, and male honour; economic instability and prolonged austerity have further weakened alignment with broader European gender-equality trajectories (Lomazzi, 2023). Greece ranks 24th in the EU on the Gender Equality Index, 12.2 points below the score for the EU as a whole, while sexual violence remains at high levels: 42% of women who have ever been in a relationship have experienced violence by an intimate partner during their adult life, while 43% of women who have ever worked have experienced sexual harassment at work.⁴ Building on this criticism, Risman (2020) highlights how crises such as COVID-19 not only expose but also strengthen gendered systems, determining who is responsible for the financial, emotional, and caregiving responsibilities.

Delving into the most recent studies, sexual violence and harassment remain significant issues within various professional and social domains in Greece, with institutional and socio-cultural factors contributing to underreporting and ineffective responses. A study examining sexual harassment in the Greek healthcare sector found that 70% of female nurses experienced some form of sexual harassment during their professional lives, with male doctors as the primary perpetrators (Papantoniou, 2021). Notably, younger nurses and those working in the

private sector reported higher rates of harassment. The findings suggest that sexual coercion and unwanted sexual attention significantly impact victims' physical health and job performance, emphasizing the need for comprehensive workplace policies to protect healthcare workers. However, 30% of victims refrained from reporting incidents due to fear of negative consequences or skepticism that any action would be taken, indicating the law enforcement and socio-cultural barriers to reporting.

The delayed onset of the #MeToo movement in Greece prompted discussions on how patriarchal and collectivist cultural values silence survivors and protect perpetrators (Chroni & Kavoura, 2022). A thematic analysis of 36 media reports revealed systemic institutional silencing and power imbalances, which discourage victims from speaking up, particularly in male-dominated spaces like sports. Similarly, efforts to combat domestic violence remain hindered by gaps in law enforcement responses. The development of the Hellenic Risk Assessment Instrument aimed at evaluating domestic violence recidivism and lethality found that police officers and frontline responders lacked standardized tools to assess and prevent escalating violence (Fotou et al., 2024). Data from domestic violence cases reported between 2019 and 2021 revealed that critical risk factors—such as previous reports of abuse, socio-economic vulnerabilities, and event-driven spikes in violence (e.g., during major sporting events and holidays)—often went unaddressed. Focus groups with Greek law enforcement professionals highlighted the absence of an integrated risk assessment framework, further complicating protective interventions for domestic violence victims (Fotou et al., 2024). Collectively, these studies underscore the persistent structural and cultural barriers that sustain gender-based violence in Greece, reinforcing the urgent need for policy reforms, trauma-informed training, and robust victim support systems.

Forensic evidence from Greece is quite limited, with most recent data indicating that GHB is detected in only 0.4% of DFSA cases in Greece, compared to 5.9% in the U.S., 3% in France, and 2% in the Netherlands (Skov et al., 2022). However, sexualized drug use (SDU) and chemsex have emerged as critical public health concerns, particularly among MSM. A survey of 485 MSM in internal medicine departments and community testing centers found that 28% engaged in SDU and 20.4% participated in chemsex, with higher HIV and STI prevalence rates among those involved in these behaviors (Poulios et al., 2022). Given the rapid rise of chemsex in Greece (Poulios et al., 2022), the low detection rates of GHB-related crimes likely stem not from low prevalence but from significant forensic and institutional shortcomings in identifying and addressing these offenses. The study underscores the urgent need for community-based health interventions addressing both sexual risk behaviors and substance use in vulnerable populations. By focusing on Greece, the study not only fills a critical regional gap in DFSA research but also highlights systemic issues in Southern Europe, where forensic infrastructures and gender-inclusive legal protections remain underdeveloped (Prego Meleiro et al., 2020).

3.2. Data collection and analysis

The research unfolded in three interconnected phases: (1) a literature review and policy analysis, (2) interviews with forensic experts, and (3) interviews with key informants to examine the specific challenges in Greece. The study followed a Constructivist Grounded Theory (CGT) approach (Charmaz, 2006), recognizing that forensic and legal challenges in GHB-related DFSA are shaped by institutional practices, socio-cultural dynamics, and the lived experiences of professionals.

More analytically, Phase 1 involved an extensive review of forensic science literature, legal frameworks, and policy reports to contextualize forensic challenges in GHB detection and legal responses to DFSA. Key areas of investigation included the short detection window of GHB, the gendered physiological differences affecting toxicological interpretations, and the forensic exclusion of male and LGBTQ+ survivors. In parallel, the study examined EU and national policies, such as the Victims' Rights Directive, the Istanbul Convention, and Greece's

⁴ https://eige.europa.eu/modules/custom/eige_gei/app/content/downloads/factsheets/EL_2023_factsheet.pdf.

National Action Plan on Gender-Based Violence (2022–2026), assessing their effectiveness in guiding forensic investigations and legal protections for DFSA victims. A key feature of this phase was the iterative integration of findings with subsequent empirical data collection, allowing for a dynamic refinement of emerging theoretical insights. While the inclusion of documentary materials would strengthen the research, in this institutional landscape, the absence of documentary materials is not a limitation of the research design but rather an empirical indicator of systemic unpreparedness. The inability to conduct documentary triangulation reflects the structural void the study seeks to illuminate: DFSA-related practices in Greece operate largely through discretionary, ad hoc, and experience-based decision-making rather than codified procedures. The absence of formalized protocols, training curricula, and administrative categorization mechanisms is itself a substantive finding that corroborates participants' accounts.

Phase 2 involved semi-structured interviews with 11 forensic experts following a criterion sampling. Participants were selected for their specialized engagement with DFSA cases (See Table 2). Experts were recruited through consortium members and stakeholder organizations within the ARMADILLO project,⁵ who facilitated contact with forensic associations, academics, and targeted invitations to institutions known to handle DFSA cases. Structured interviews were conducted online in English using a secure digital survey platform, with access restricted exclusively to the individual participant responding to the interview to ensure confidentiality and data protection.

Phase 3 involved 13 semi-structured interviews with key informants embedded in Greek institutional and frontline contexts. Sampling followed Constructivist Grounded Theory (CGT) principles (Charmaz, 2006) and was designed for analytic coverage of the institutional processes shaping GHB-related DFSA. Theoretical sampling was used to recruit participants positioned along the DFSA response chain in Greece (forensic toxicology/forensic medicine; policing; healthcare; gender-equality/policy; community/NGO/harm reduction; LGBTQ+—informed services). Inclusion criteria required that participants (a) had direct professional involvement with DFSA-related incidents, investigations, toxicology, clinical response, policy implementation, or community response; and (b) could speak to institutional procedures, constraints, and interpretive practices relevant to GHB-related DFSA. Recruitment pathways included purposive outreach through professional networks and institutional contacts. Participation was voluntary and based on informed consent. Interviews were conducted either in person or online, depending on participant preference and confidentiality requirements and they lasted 45–60 min, were conducted in Greek, audio-recorded with consent, professionally transcribed verbatim, and verified for accuracy by the research team.

Interviews explored survivors' experiences as understood through frontline professionals, stigma and victim-blaming, particularly affecting male and LGBTQ + victims, mechanisms of institutional silencing within forensic, police, and healthcare systems, implementation gaps between national policy frameworks and real-world investigative practices. It should be noted that while several interviewees referred to GHB in their anecdotal accounts of DFSA, these testimonies reflect professional perceptions and experiential knowledge rather than verified epidemiological prevalence. The frequency of GHB involvement in such cases cannot be conclusively established on the basis of interview data alone and remains constrained by the well-documented limitations of toxicological detection and reporting systems.

Survivors were excluded from direct participation to prevent retraumatization and ensure ethical integrity, as discussing DFSA experiences can trigger psychological distress. While the exclusion of survivors from direct participation was ethically necessary, this decision also carries significant epistemic implications that must be acknowledged. In line with account of epistemic injustice, the absence of

survivor voices reinforces broader epistemic hierarchies through which institutional actors are positioned as the primary bearers of legitimate knowledge (Fricker, 2007). Consequently, the insights generated in this study derive primarily from institutional, professional, and systemic standpoints, rather than from the embodied experiences of individuals who have survived GHB-related DFSA. The analytic categories and the emergent theoretical model should therefore be read as reflecting how forensic experts, law enforcement authorities, healthcare professionals, policymakers, and community actors conceptualize and navigate the phenomenon.

Consistent with CGT, sampling was not fully predetermined; it evolved in response to emerging analysis. Early interviews with forensic experts produced recurring accounts of (i) rapid metabolism and narrow detection windows (“GHB disappears fast”; “10–12 h in urine”), and (ii) memory disruption (“you do not have the ability to recall”). Through constant comparison, these observations were consolidated into the developing category forensic temporal fragility (i.e., evidence becomes unavailable before reporting is feasible).

This category generated a theoretical question guiding further recruitment: How do institutional actors interpret and handle DFSA allegations when toxicology is negative due to reporting delays? To address this, we theoretically sampled police and procedural actors, and revised the interview guide to include questions on evidentiary thresholds, credibility assessment, and decision-making under uncertainty. This step enabled identification of evidentiary hierarchy, reflected in accounts where negative toxicology was treated as proof of non-occurrence (e.g., “as has been proven ... they do not exist”).

As the analytic focus sharpened on procedural handling, additional theoretical sampling targeted institutional gender-equality and healthcare actors to test whether “procedural vacuum” and “lack of training” were localized to policing or structurally distributed across institutions. This extended and refined the category institutional unpreparedness (e.g., “We are not at all informed”; “Doctors have called from ERs to ask what to do”), and linked it to institutional silencing via mistrust, anticipated stigma, and avoidance of reporting (“police is not an institution women trust”; “a trans person might be arrested rather than helped”).

Finally, the emergence of accounts of “blurred consent” and under-recognition of coercion in chemsex-related contexts prompted targeted inclusion of LGBTQ+—informed professionals and harm-reduction actors. Interview questions were adapted to probe how consent is negotiated under intoxication, what counts as “abuse” within sexualized drug use settings, and how heteronormative service infrastructures shape disclosure (“support services are designed for straight people ...”). This iterative process continued until categories were sufficiently elaborated across domains.

Interviews were transcribed and analysed concurrently with data collection. All participants were assigned anonymized identification codes (e.g., Int1, Int2) at the point of transcription, and any potentially identifying details were removed or generalized to prevent deductive disclosure. Analysis followed CGT procedures (Charmaz, 2006) using iterative coding, constant comparison, and memo-writing. Initial open coding was conducted line-by-line to stay close to participants' meanings and language, generating *in vivo* and process-oriented codes (e.g., “GHB disappears fast,” “no training,” “everything is done empirically,” “they do not exist”). Axial coding then selected the most frequent and analytically powerful codes and synthesized them into higher-order, explanatory codes. For example, statements about the detection window and delayed reporting were integrated into a focused code capturing time-dependent evidentiary vulnerability, which developed into forensic temporal fragility. Similarly, police statements treating negative toxicology as proof of non-occurrence were coded as toxicology-based credibility gating, forming the category evidentiary hierarchy. Selective coding linked categories into a process model describing how pharmacology, evidentiary practices, and institutional infrastructures interact to produce underreporting and case attrition.

⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101168416>.

Throughout analysis, constant comparison was applied (within interviews, across professional domains, and across phases) to refine category properties, identify contradictions, and test emerging interpretations. Memo-writing documented analytic decisions (e.g., why a category was retained/merged, how a discrepancy was interpreted, what “gap” required theoretical sampling). Memos were also used reflexively to examine how the researchers’ interdisciplinary positioning (forensic, socio-legal, and gender-analytic lenses) shaped interpretive choices. Table 3 (see Appendix) provides illustrative examples tracing analytic movement from empirical material to initial codes, focused codes, and conceptual categories, including the theoretical sampling decisions these categories generated.

Theoretical saturation was assessed analytically rather than mechanically. We considered categories saturated when additional interviews no longer generated new properties of core categories, and when relationships between categories remained stable under further comparison across domains (e.g., forensic, policing, healthcare, community). The final dataset includes 24 interviews (11 + 13); reporting has been corrected to remove prior numerical inconsistencies. In the revised Results, saturation is supported by cross-domain recurrence of the same category properties (e.g., time-dependent evidence loss; toxicology as credibility gate; lack of protocol/training; mistrust and avoidance; blurred consent and heteronormative service design).

3.3. Ethical considerations

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical guidelines of the ARMADILLO project, which is co-funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101168416. All procedures adhered to the ethical standards outlined in the Horizon Europe Programme Guide, the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ALLEA – All European Academies, 2017), and Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data (GDPR).

All participants received a detailed information sheet outlining the aims of the study, the voluntary nature of participation, the types of data collected, potential risks, and their right to withdraw at any time without consequence. Informed consent was obtained prior to each interview, in written form. Participants were explicitly informed that they could refuse to answer any question, pause or terminate the interview at any point, and request the deletion of their data. To safeguard participants’ privacy, all interview transcripts were fully anonymized. Any contextual details that could inadvertently lead to identification were generalized. Data were processed in full compliance with GDPR and Horizon Europe data protection requirements. Digital files (transcripts, consent forms, coding frameworks) were stored on encrypted, password-protected institutional servers with restricted access granted only to authorised members of the research team.

4. Results

4.1. Forensic and institutional challenges in the Greek context

From an epidemiological standpoint, GHB has become a common substance used in sexual assaults due to its effects on disinhibition, memory loss, and motor control. Victims frequently report sudden incapacitation, confusion, and inability to recall events. Interviewees confirmed the relevant literature based on their field experiences: as one psychiatrist explained, “GHB removes inhibitions, causes memory and consciousness disturbances ... the body becomes limp” (Int14). The drug induces what is known as anterograde amnesia, where individuals are unable to form memories during the period of intoxication. Similarly a forensic expert stressed that “you do not have the ability to recall events later ... the primary mechanism causing the amnesia is the loss of consciousness that the person experiences” (Int8). This makes the recollection and reporting of the assault especially difficult. Even when victims

do come forward, the forensic timeline works against them. “GHB is mainly detected in urine for 10–12 h. The literature states up to 18 h, but these are not at toxic levels,” one toxicologist noted, adding that in practice, “If they come after three weeks, the results will be negative ... That doesn’t mean they weren’t drugged” (Int9). As the forensic expert further emphasized, “The sooner we get the urine, the better. GHB disappears fast” (Int9).

Despite these forensic limitations that are well-recorded in the relevant literature, drawing on the absence of toxicological evidence, police seemed to discredit survivors. One police officer handling sexual assaults stated, “In theory they are reported, but as has been proven by the investigation and toxicological tests, they do not exist” (Int20). In addition, victims frequently delay reporting due to confusion, stigma, or fear. Forensic experts highlighted that “It is a long period of time for the victim to decide to report” (Int9), and “from our experience, incidents of actual rapes take time to come to us. It will be several days later” (Int8). In regard to the institutional environment, a social servant highlighted there was a widespread “shame and lack of trust in competent institutions” (Int13). The police were seen as particularly untrustworthy. “The police is not an institution that women trust to make a report. It’s among those with the lowest level of public confidence” (Int15). This mistrust is intensified for marginalized populations as one academic on gender studies emphasized: “If a trans person is assaulted and goes to the police, they might be arrested rather than helped” (Int17).

Empirical evidence from interviews with police officers from the police headquarters supports these findings, revealing a lack of consistency, structured procedures, and specialized training in responses to DFSA. As one officer acknowledged, they are often ill-equipped to handle cases involving substance-related sexual violence: “We have no training. [We do] what the forensic experts tell us” (Int20). The description of how police authorities handle potential victims of DFSA is quite informative (Int19; Int20): there is an official list of psychologists provided by the Public Prosecutor’s Office, and their presence in a victim’s statement is considered rather helpful. However, in practice, DFSA complaints can be filed at any time of the day or night, even at three in the morning, which makes it difficult to always have a listed psychologist available. In that case, a police psychologist might step in but again finding one at the right time is not always easy. One way or another, even when there is an available psychologist, their role is merely to assess whether the victim is mentally capable of giving a statement as a witness, but not to comment on the incident itself. Notably, the presence of a female officer when a woman reports a DFSA is not mandated by law. It was quite unexpected that in the researched police headquarters a male officer was assigned to handle such cases, something he himself admitted might not always make female victims feel comfortable. While the police officers interviewed acknowledged this gap and stated that they strive to have a female officer present during the statement, they also admitted that this is not always possible. In some departments, no female officers may be on duty or available at the time of the report. Crucially, there is no formal protocol to ensure such supportive practices are consistently followed; instead, it depends entirely on the individual officer’s experience, discretion, and empathy. As one of the police officers highlighted “everything is done empirically. There is no protocol for handling rape incidents” (Int19). In a question on whether this is something that exposes police officers themselves, the reply was a strong “Definitely” (Int19), pointing to the fact that protocols would be also valuable for the law enforcement authorities too. They themselves gave the example of a recent law for domestic violence, which by providing protocols made their work easier and brought them into contact with NGOs that could provide support to the victims.

The absence of formal protocols was not limited to police authorities but extended to the General Secretariat for Gender Equality and Human Rights—an institution that often serves as the first point of contact for DFSA complaints. A social servant openly admitted, “We are not at all informed ... I am alone, I have noticed it, it has been weighing on me ... and no, I am not informed at all” (Int13). Similar deficits were evident

within the healthcare sector, where a combination of under-skilling and chronic understaffing severely undermines the response to substance-related sexual violence (Int14). As one psychiatrist observed, “In our training, there’s nothing specific about sexual violence involving substances. No one teaches you what GHB is” (Int14). Echoing this, a clinical psychotherapist specialized on chemsex noted the ad hoc nature of medical responses: “Doctors have called me from Emergency Rooms to ask what to do ... That’s not their fault. It’s a systemic issue” (Int18). Hospitals, too, lack basic preparedness. “Neither our doctors are trained ... and we also do not have trained nurses,” one expert emphasized (Int8). These gaps are equally apparent to frontline harm reduction workers as an NGO representative underlined “We want to do training for nursing staff, because there’s a knowledge gap there ... knowledge that either these teams have to have or be close to awareness teams” (Int21). As an activist pointed out, public education is also lacking: “We need to break taboos. People need to know what drugs are, what consent is, what a safe space is” (Int16). The urgent need to enhance the institutional framework was underscored by a recent positive shift that has been the outcome of an institutional change according to a police officer: “Lately they [victims] have been coming more often to report because a paragraph has been added to the law about the [sexual] consent of both. This even includes extreme intoxication” (Int19).

This constellation of factors is conceptualized here as forensic temporal fragility, that is, a structural condition in which the rapid metabolism and endogenous presence of GHB, combined with inevitable reporting delays, undermine the production of confirmatory toxicological evidence. Within this fragile evidentiary framework, institutional reliance on toxicological confirmation establishes what we term an evidentiary hierarchy, whereby laboratory results are privileged over survivor testimony and experiential accounts. In such a hierarchy, the absence of toxicological proof can be transformed into institutional disbelief. Thus, strong assertions by police authorities that such incidents “do not exist,” rather than acknowledging that they remain unproven, reveal not merely individual misunderstanding but a systemic misalignment between pharmacological realities and institutional interpretation. The intersection of delayed reporting and narrow detection windows generates a self-reinforcing cycle: evidentiary absence fosters skepticism, skepticism discourages reporting, and reduced reporting further obscures the phenomenon. In this way, forensic limitation becomes institutional denial, contributing to patterns of attrition and abandonment within the justice process.

4.2. Socio-cultural challenges: fear, stigmatization and the normalization of sexual violence

According to a policy advocate who presented results from recent research “9/10 women have been harassed at least once at work,” while she further explained how coercion is often disguised: “It often starts with ‘you have a beautiful smile’ - and escalates from there. But because there’s an initial moment of consent to the interaction, victims feel trapped later and blame themselves” (Int15). The inability to identify coercion as violence has even affected Greek feminist discourse, which, the advocate argued, remained disengaged from DFSA issues until high-profile cases like that of Georgia Bika⁶ catalyzed public attention. The invisibility of this violence is particularly stark in nightlife environments. One woman who worked for years in the night scene had described her daily existence to the policy advocate as one of constant fear: “According to her words: I live like the prey in the jungle ... the predators are ready to eat me” (Int15). In the same vein, an activist that

worked in the night scene recounted that drug-facilitated sexual violence has long plagued the music scene, describing a known promoter who “raped women over a period of 20–25 years using substances. No one stopped him” (Int16). Her testimony extends beyond heterosexual encounters, highlighting cases of gay men waking up in group sex settings they had not consented to and could not remember. The lack of institutional accountability remained a major concern: “There are no safe spaces, no awareness, no education ... no trust in institutions ... Only 7% of people we surveyed said they would go to the police” (Int16).

According to a clinical psychologist, silence is often maintained through powerful mechanisms of stigma and shame, particularly around gender, drug use, sexuality, and HIV status. In this context, survivors frequently internalize guilt. “They carry a lot of guilt already ... because ‘I wanted to party’ or ‘I was high’ - that’s the trauma” (Int18). This internalized stigma is compounded by external societal reactions that frame victims as complicit. As the social worker observed, “They [rapists] have a way of making them somewhat complicit in this, which, let’s say, with the older, ‘classic’ rapes without this pill, there was no such thing” (Int1). Stigma also extends to the venues themselves. Many refuse to acknowledge the presence of substance use or violence for fear of reputational damage. As reported by an NGO representative working in the field, “Some venues didn’t want us to put materials on our booth because they didn’t want it to seem like people use drugs there-though they do”. The activist added, “We tried putting up a basic poster: ‘No harassment. No abuse. Only good vibes.’ Even gay venues refused. They said, ‘If we put it up, it will look like this happens here’” (Int16).

An activist indicated that “the person has shame, fear, trauma ... They don’t know what to do. They don’t even know they can go to a hospital and ask for a rape kit” (Int16). Fear of institutional neglect persists: “Only 7% said they would go to the police. We even documented rapes inside police stations” (Int16). In response, her collective developed a digital tool to map safe and inclusive spaces, recognizing that “people go out afraid to leave their drink alone or walk home at night” (Int16). This lack of visibility is particularly pronounced in cases involving chemsex drugs. As an interviewee from the NGO emphasized, users of these substances are “not out in the streets, but are couch users,” rendering the phenomenon socially invisible and often excluded from public discourse. Even more striking is that indoor GHB use has remained largely invisible within toxicological detection.

The findings indicate that sexual coercion operates within a socio-cultural environment marked by socio-cultural normalization and prevention gap, where harassment is frequently rendered ordinary and the boundary between consent and manipulation becomes blurred. This normalization is compounded by institutional unpreparedness and a broader procedural vacuum and discretionary handling of cases, which intensify ambiguity and contribute to survivor disempowerment and underreporting. Such dynamics are particularly pronounced in contexts of recreational GHB use, especially within LGBTQ + chemsex settings, where intoxication destabilizes conventional understandings of consent and complicates legal recognition of harm. The convergence of normalization, institutional unpreparedness, and evidentiary uncertainty points to an underexplored dimension of DFSA: the reconceptualization of sexual violence under conditions of substance-mediated ambiguity, particularly among LGBTQ + individuals.

4.3. LGBTQ + experiences: from blurred consent to institutional neglect

Sexual violence in LGBTQ + contexts -especially those involving chemsex and GHB- is characterized by blurred lines of consent, making violations difficult to identify or prove. A clinical psychologist and chemsex expert explained that “consent becomes complex when I give consent not to give consent,” noting that under the influence of GHB, “you become highly submissive and may consent to something you wouldn’t sober” (Int18). In this light, the boundaries between agency and coercion collapse, particularly in party settings where “people make use of substances and engage in sex, but the boundaries blur” (Int21). As

⁶ A high-profile case involved a woman who reported being drug-facilitated raped on New Year’s Eve 2022 by a member of the so-called ‘high-class’ society. Despite her efforts to seek justice, her case remains unresolved. <https://diotima.org/en/dikaivosyni-gia-ti-georgia-amesa-metra-prostasias-gia-oles-tis-epi-zoses-viasmoy/>.

Tsui (2024) argues, the concept of bounded non-normativity enables individuals to compartmentalize normative identities and non-normative practices, preserving public respectability while privately satisfying stigmatized desires. In these settings, what often starts as voluntary GHB usage for recreational purposes after a while can become and often become coercive. In the end, victims (mostly men) find themselves “naked in someone’s home, surrounded by 20 people having sex. They didn’t even know how they got there” (Int16). Anecdotal accounts from LGBTQ + communities corroborated this phenomenon, with researchers encountering a couple of strikingly similar narratives from gay men during the study period. In this process, internalized shame further complicates trauma processing “they [victims] carry a lot of guilt ... and with the intersecting stigma of not being straight, of using drugs, maybe even living with HIV, they feel like they can’t even identify what happened as abuse” (Int18). Shame, more than guilt, is “a more corrosive and difficult emotion” that traps victims in silence. This emotional paralysis is matched by systemic failures. “Hospitals are a lottery ... it depends on who you get,” (Int18) the chemsex expert remarked, while a psychiatrist added that “most professionals don’t even know what GHB is,” and that medical training includes “nothing specific about sexual violence” (Int14). He summarized GHB’s effects succinctly: “disinhibition, memory disturbances, and muscle relaxation ... you melt, and there is no physical ability to resist” (Int14), i.e. what is often described as a G-hole.

For LGBTQ + individuals and sex workers, the situation seems especially dire. “Imagine telling an officer: ‘I was taking drugs and someone raped me during that’ says the chemsex expert. “A trans sex worker raped with GHB- where will she go? Who will listen to her?” (Int18), he added. Few grassroots organizations such as the interviewed NGO have attempted to fill this void by providing harm reduction services in nightlife venues. “We saw people overdose from GHB during our very first intervention,” they reported, noting the substance’s transition from gay to straight club scenes. Despite repeated incidents of drink spiking and blackouts, few cases ever reach the authorities. “We can treat and support people on the spot, but we’re not the police. If the organizer is sensitive, they’ll intervene. Otherwise, nothing happens” (Int21). Even within LGBTQ + spaces, awareness remains limited. “There is widespread use, but very limited understanding of the risks. People don’t even know what these substances do” (Int21), said a team member from the NGO. Their interventions -including drug-checking, safe use kits, and psychological first aid-have become a best -and unfortunately rare-practice in the absence of institutional care.

As the policy advocate concluded, “There’s a whole spectrum that plays with consent-where the victim might not even realize they’re being manipulated”. Services, meanwhile, remain heteronormative and inaccessible. According to the chemsex expert’s words “support services are often designed for straight people using alcohol or heroin”, noting that victims “go to an STI clinic and only then, in passing, mention the incident—because that’s the only place they feel safe to talk” (Int18). As the policy advocate puts it, “I can imagine trans girls with multiple vulnerabilities ... There is no validation, no justice” (Int15).

Sexual violence in LGBTQ + contexts -particularly within chemsex environments involving GHB- reveals what emerged analytically as blurred consent in chemsex contexts, where intoxication destabilizes agency and renders the identification and legal substantiation of violations profoundly complex. This ambiguity does not operate in isolation but intersects with what the analysis conceptualized as heteronormative service design and LGBTQ + neglect, whereby institutional responses remain structured around assumptions of heterosexual victimhood and alcohol-based intoxication. Together, blurred consent and heteronormative institutional design contribute to the structural invisibility of substance-facilitated sexual violence within marginalized communities.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that the underreporting of GHB-related

drug-facilitated sexual assault in Greece cannot be explained solely by toxicological limitations, but emerges from the interaction between pharmacological properties, evidentiary practices, institutional infrastructures, and socio-cultural norms. The rapid metabolism and endogenous presence of GHB produce what we conceptualized as forensic temporal fragility, while institutional reliance on toxicological confirmation creates an evidentiary hierarchy that can convert uncertainty into disbelief. These forensic dynamics intersect with procedural vacuum and institutional unpreparedness, where the absence of standardized protocols and training results in discretionary handling and inconsistent survivor experiences. At the same time, stigma, mistrust, and heteronormative service design contribute to institutional silencing, particularly affecting women and LGBTQ + individuals, especially within chemsex contexts where consent becomes blurred and difficult to legally articulate. Taken together, the findings reveal that the invisibility of GHB-related DFSA in Greece reflects not a lack of occurrence but a structural misalignment between lived experiences of victimization and institutional capacities to recognize, document, and respond to them. Addressing this gap requires systemic reform that integrates forensic precision with trauma-informed, gender-sensitive, and intersectionally inclusive institutional frameworks.

In terms of research gaps, direct testimonies from DFSA survivors were not included in this study, which restricted access to first-hand recollections that might provide important insights into personal victimization experiences, reporting obstacles, and institutional involvement. Furthermore, the research was carried out in Greece, where there is still a lack of thorough data, documentary material and a lack of public awareness regarding GHB-facilitated sexual assault. The inability to thoroughly capture the prevalence and extent of the phenomenon or make more general conclusions is hampered by the lack of nationally collected datasets. In this vein, it is important to analytically distinguish between toxicological detection rates, epidemiological prevalence, and sociocultural visibility of GHB-related DFSA. Low laboratory detection rates do not necessarily indicate low incidence, as detection depends on timely sampling, testing protocols, interpretive cut-offs, and institutional capacity. Similarly, increased media attention or survivor testimony reflects sociocultural visibility rather than directly measurable prevalence. Accordingly, cross-national comparisons must be interpreted cautiously, given variations in forensic infrastructure, reporting systems, and monitoring frameworks across countries.

In parallel following a Constructivist Grounded Theory this study recognized that knowledge is co-constructed through interaction between researcher and participants (Charmaz, 2006). Positionality therefore became analytically relevant rather than incidental. Within this study, the primary interviewer’s male identity initially introduced constraints on disclosure, particularly when engaging with professionals working closely with women and LGBTQ + survivors of sexual violence. This dynamic echoes established findings in research involving marginalized populations, where gendered power and symbolic capital shape the research encounter (Belur, 2013). In several early interviews, caution was perceptible, particularly when discussing institutional disbelief, LGBTQ + marginalization, and chemsex-related practices. However, positionality operated relationally rather than deterministically. As Obasi (2021) demonstrates in Deaf research, difference does not automatically preclude trust; rather, participants evaluate researchers through perceived intent, accountability, and reciprocity. In the context of DFSA, the presence of a straight male researcher was initially met with guarded engagement but gradually reinterpreted by some participants as a willingness to listen from outside entrenched institutional hierarchies. Just as participants assessed whether the research encounter constituted a safe space for disclosure, survivors of DFSA continuously assess whether institutional settings will offer recognition or reproduce harm.

It is precisely this parallel that underscores the urgency of increasing public and institutional visibility around GHB-related DFSA. Future approaches must bring affected communities into the spotlight, not as

objects of regulation but as agents of knowledge and accountability. Acknowledging the local reality of GHB-DFSA is a necessary step toward breaking the silence, fostering community accountability, building informed, context-sensitive prevention strategies and triggering institutional responses. In this light, we need to reverse the logic often used to avoid awareness campaigns, namely, *"If we put this up, it will look like this happens here."* Instead, we must assert emphatically: *this happens here, and that's exactly why we need to put it up.*

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Georgios Chatzichristos: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Eri Eleftheria Papadopoulou:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Ethical approval

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical guidelines of the ARMADILLO project, which is co-funded by the European Union's

Appendix

Table 1
Research Design

Research Stage	Phase 1	Phase 2	Phase 3
Research Objective(s)	Reviewing forensic and socio-cultural challenges	Explore in-depth insights for forensic challenges	Exploring the Greek context of GHB-related DFSA
Research Tool	Literature review and report analysis	Structured interviews	Semi-structured interviews
Research subjects/ objects		Experts on DFSA	Greek key informants on GHB-DFSA

Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101168416. All procedures followed the ethical standards set out in the Horizon Europe Programme Guide, the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ALLEA – All European Academies, 2017), and Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data (GDPR).

Statements and declarations

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Table 2

Interviewee	Field	Expertise
Int1	Law enforcement	Police Officer, Criminologist
Int2	Forensic	Expert on diagnostics
Int3	Law enforcement	Police Officer
Int4	Technology	Expert on sensor development
Int5	Forensic	Forensic Geneticist
Int6	Law enforcement	Drug enforcement Agency
Int7	Law enforcement	Drug enforcement Agency
Int11	Diagnostics	PhD candidate in analytical chemistry
Excluded	Non-informative	
Int22	Technology	Cyber Security
Int23	Law enforcement	Police Officer
Int24	Law enforcement	Police Officer
Greece		
Int8	Forensic	Pr in Toxicology
Int9	Forensic	Expert in Toxicology
Int10	Diagnostics	PhD candidate in diagnostic accuracy
Int12	Diagnostics	Dr in Chemistry
Int13	Public Services	Social worker in: General Secretariat for Equality and Human Rights
Int14	Psychology-Psychiatry	Psychiatrist, Msc in Gender Studies
Int15	Policy Advocacy	Researcher, Policy advocate in UNICEF
Int16	Activist, night scene	Activist working in the night scene
Int17	Academia	Pr in Political Sciences, focus on gender studies
Int18	Academia-Psychology	Lecturer, Clinical Psychologist, Chemsex expert
Int19	Law enforcement	Chief Police Officer

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Table 2 (continued)

Interviewee	Field	Expertise
Int20	Law enforcement	Police Officer, expertise on sexual assaults
Int21	Nightlife	NGO working for the safe use of drugs

Table 3
CGT analytic movement from empirical material to conceptual categories (illustrative examples)

Exemplar empirical material (interview)	Open code (line-by-line/in vivo)	Axial code (analytic synthesis)	Selective code- Higher-level category (CGT)	Analytic memo/theoretical sampling link (how it shaped next data collection/model)
“GHB removes inhibitions, causes memory and consciousness disturbances ... the body becomes limp.” (Int14)	“body becomes limp”; “consciousness disturbances”	Pharmacological incapacitation as assault-enabling condition	Pharmacological incapacitation	Established a mechanism linking intoxication to inability to resist → led to probing how institutions interpret “incapacitation” vs “consent.”
“You do not have the ability to recall events later ... the primary mechanism causing the amnesia is the loss of consciousness ...” (Int8)	“cannot recall”; “loss of consciousness”	Memory loss as structural barrier to disclosure	Cognitive/temporal disruption of reporting	Raised question: if memory is disrupted, how do victims meet reporting/evidence requirements? Prompted deeper questioning on timelines and evidentiary thresholds.
“GHB is mainly detected in urine for 10–12 h ... If they come after three weeks, the results will be negative ... That doesn't mean they weren't drugged.” (Int9)	“negative doesn't mean not drugged”; “10–12 h”	Evidence becomes unavailable before reporting is feasible	Forensic temporal fragility	Triggered theoretical sampling toward police/prosecutorial actors to examine what negative toxicology <i>does</i> institutionally to case legitimacy.
“The sooner we get the urine, the better. GHB disappears fast.” (Int9)	“disappears fast”; “sooner is better”	Time-dependent evidentiary vulnerability	Forensic temporal fragility	Consolidated the “time” property of the category; guided revision of interview guide to include questions on chain-of-custody and timing practices.
“In theory they are reported, but as has been proven by the investigation and toxicological tests, they do not exist.” (Int20)	“do not exist” because tests negative	Absence-of-evidence treated as evidence-of-absence	Evidentiary hierarchy/toxicology as credibility gate	Confirmed institutional translation of forensic uncertainty into denial → led to sampling of gender-equality/policy actors to examine system-level consequences of disbelief.
“It is a long period of time for the victim to decide to report.” (Int9)	“long time to decide”	Delay shaped by shame/confusion/fear	Delayed reporting as socio-forensic interface	Functioned as bridge code linking stigma to forensic temporal fragility; prompted targeted questions about mistrust and anticipated institutional harm.
“Incidents of actual rapes take time to come to us. It will be several days later.” (Int8)	“several days later”	Routine misalignment between lived reporting time and forensic window	Delayed reporting as socio-forensic interface	Strengthened cross-domain comparison: forensic experts normalize delay → contrasted with police claims of “non-existence,” sharpening the emerging process model.
“We have no training. [We do] what the forensic experts tell us.” (Int20)	“no training”; “we do what experts tell us”	Delegation + procedural uncertainty	Institutional unpreparedness	Prompted theoretical sampling of healthcare/secretariat to test whether “unpreparedness” is systemic or sector-specific.
“Everything is done empirically. There is no protocol for handling rape incidents.” (Int19)	“empirically”; “no protocol”	Discretion replaces standardized procedure	Procedural vacuum and discretionary handling	Added property: outcomes depend on individual empathy/availability → guided questions about variability, liability, and secondary victimization.
“We are not at all informed ... I am alone ... and no, I am not informed at all.” (Int13)	“not informed”; “alone”	First-contact institutional incapacity	Institutional unpreparedness/ institutional silencing	Demonstrated that failure occurs outside policing too → supported theorization of “institutional silencing” as system-level condition, not individual failure.
“In our training, there's nothing specific ... No one teaches you what GHB is.” (Int14)	“no one teaches what GHB is”	Knowledge gap embedded in professional formation	Professional knowledge deficit	Strengthened argument that technical fixes alone are insufficient; led to targeted questions on training needs and institutional responsibility.
“Doctors have called me from Emergency Rooms to ask what to do ... That's not their fault. It's a systemic issue.” (Int18)	“ER doctors ask what to do”; “systemic issue”	Ad hoc care pathways + systemic responsibility shift	Systemic fragmentation of response	Connected healthcare gaps to reporting attrition; informed the model's “systemic barriers to justice” pathway.
“The police is not an institution that women trust to make a report ... lowest level of public confidence.” (Int15)	“police not trusted”	Anticipated institutional harm discourages reporting	Institutional mistrust and avoidance	Prompted deeper probing of marginalized groups' risk calculus and the consequences of mistrust for evidence collection.
“If a trans person is assaulted and goes to the police, they might be arrested rather than helped.” (Int17)	“might be arrested”	Institutional risk for marginalized survivors	Intersectional vulnerability/ anticipatory criminalization	Drove theoretical sampling toward LGBTQ+/-harm-reduction actors; refined category properties (fear, invisibility, service mismatch).
“We need to break taboos ... know what drugs are, what consent is, what a safe space is.” (Int16)	“break taboos”; “safe space”	Prevention requires cultural/institutional change	Socio-cultural normalization and prevention gap	Linked socio-cultural normalization to institutional neglect; supported recommendations beyond toxicology (education, safe spaces, harm reduction).
“Only 7% ... said they would go to the police.” (Int16)	“only 7% would go”	Extremely low reporting intention	Institutional silencing and underreporting	Helped justify “underreporting” as outcome of combined stigma + mistrust + procedural vacuum; supported model outcome node.
“Consent becomes complex when I give consent not to give consent ... under	“consent not to consent”; “submissive”	Substance-mediated ambiguity in agency	Blurred consent in chemsex contexts	Shaped interview guide to probe consent narratives and institutional interpretive frames

(continued on next page)

Table 3 (continued)

Exemplar empirical material (interview)	Open code (line-by-line/in vivo)	Axial code (analytic synthesis)	Selective code- Higher-level category (CGT)	Analytic memo/theoretical sampling link (how it shaped next data collection/model)
GHB, you become highly submissive ...” (Int18) “Support services are often designed for straight people ... victims mention the incident only in passing ... at an STI clinic.” (Int18)	“services designed for straight people”	Heteronormative infrastructure blocks disclosure	Heteronormative service design/LGBTQ + neglect	for LGBTQ + contexts (consent, blame, credibility). Added institutional pathway: disclosure displaced to “safer” niche services → strengthened argument for inclusive, specialized response systems.

Table 4

From Emergent Categories to Institutional Implications

Emergent Analytic Category	Illustrative Empirical Evidence	Identified Structural Problem	Data-Derived Institutional Implications
Forensic Temporal Fragility	“GHB disappears fast.” (Int9)/“Detected 10–12 h ... negative doesn’t mean not drugged.” (Int9)	Rapid metabolism + reporting delays lead to evidentiary loss and case attrition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mandatory immediate blood and urine sampling protocols • Dual-phase hair sampling in delayed cases • Multi-drug toxicology screening • Forensic reports must explicitly state that negative toxicology does not exclude prior exposure
Evidentiary Hierarchy (Toxicology as Credibility Gate)	“As has been proven by toxicological tests, they do not exist.” (Int20)	Absence of toxicological confirmation interpreted as absence of assault	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Judicial/prosecutorial interpretive guidelines on negative toxicology • Training on evidentiary uncertainty in DFSA • Integration of testimonial evidence alongside toxicology
Institutional Unpreparedness/ Procedural Vacuum	“Everything is done empirically. There is no protocol.” (Int19)/“We have no training.” (Int20)	Ad hoc handling; discretionary decision-making; inconsistent survivor experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National DFSA-specific standardized procedures • Mandatory interdisciplinary training (police, forensic, healthcare) • Institutionalized forensic nursing roles • Trauma-informed interviewing protocols • Anonymous and digital reporting mechanisms
Institutional Silencing and Mistrust	“The police is not an institution that women trust.” (Int15)/“Only 7% would go to the police.” (Int16)	Anticipated disbelief and discrimination discourage reporting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survivor advocates available at first contact • Legal clarification of intoxication-impaired consent • Specialized training on chemsex-related DFSA • Harm-reduction partnerships in nightlife venues
Blurred Consent in Chemsex Contexts	“Consent becomes complex when I give consent not to give consent.” (Int18)	Substance-mediated ambiguity complicates legal recognition of coercion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LGBTQ + -inclusive forensic and healthcare training • Dedicated advocates for LGBTQ + survivors • Explicit anti-discrimination safeguards in DFSA handling
Heteronormative Service Design/LGBTQ + Exclusion	“Support services are designed for straight people.” (Int18)/“A trans person might be arrested rather than helped.” (Int17)	Marginalized survivors avoid institutional systems due to fear of discrimination	

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